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ERMIS: Cybersecurity Market Assurance and Insurance-As-A-Service

Deliverable D6.1 The roadmap for the validation of cybersecurity assurance and insurance as-a- Service

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1. LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CAGR	Compound annual growth rate
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
CIEP	Cyber Insurance External Providers
CSEP	Cybersecurity Solution External Providers
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NIS2	Network and Information Security 2 Directive
OA	Organisation Administrator
SME	Small and Midsize Enterprises
TIN	Tax Identification Number
TOBA	Terms of Business Agreement
VAT	Value Added Tax

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4. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ERMIS marketplace seeks to transform the cybersecurity insurance ecosystem by creating an integrated platform that combines cybersecurity technologies with customised insurance products. This project addresses the growing demand for comprehensive risk management solutions against growing cyber threats, particularly among SME businesses. The ERMIS marketplace provides a comprehensive strategy that allows organisations to analyse their cybersecurity risks, execute effective mitigation measures, and get appropriate insurance coverage.

This document provides the structure and purpose of the ERMIS marketplace, detailing the key components of the cybersecurity insurance ecosystem, including risk assessment, incident response, compliance management, and technology solutions. It also outlines the key stakeholders, market dynamics, and the challenges in delivering cyber insurance services. It explores the business scenarios that illustrate how different entities such as SMEs, cybersecurity solution providers and cyber insurance providers, can engage with the ERMIS marketplace. These scenarios demonstrate the operation and benefits of the ERMIS marketplace for both supply and demand side parties. They also show how the platform enables the registration, validation, and administration of cybersecurity and insurance products, as well as the customisation and delivery of bundled solutions according to individual customer requirements.

Finally, the document further describes the procedure for the pilot evaluation and defines methodologies and key performance indicators to assess the platform's efficiency and effectiveness. The ERMIS marketplace represents a significant step forward in enhancing cybersecurity resilience and preparedness of businesses in an increasingly digital world. By coordinating cyber risk assessment, insurance policy tailoring, and dynamic security assurance, ERMIS platform offers a single, easy-to-use platform for complete cybersecurity.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to establish a structured roadmap for validating and deploying an integrated cybersecurity assurance and insurance model through the ERMIS marketplace. By outlining key market challenges, regulatory considerations, and evaluation methodologies, this document ensures that ERMIS delivers a scalable and efficient cyber risk management solution. A key component of this document is the detailed business scenarios and step-by-step processes that illustrate how different stakeholders—SMEs, cyber insurance providers, and cybersecurity solution providers—interact within the ERMIS marketplace. These scenarios provide real-world examples of how organisations can assess their cybersecurity risks, select tailored insurance policies, and integrate assurance solutions to strengthen their security posture. The document breaks down each scenario into clear and structured steps. By detailing these workflows, the roadmap ensures that all participants in the ERMIS platform—from insurers to insured entities—have a transparent, standardised, and user-friendly experience. These structured scenarios also support the validation and refinement of the ERMIS framework, ensuring its effectiveness in bridging the gap between cybersecurity assurance and cyber insurance in a seamless, data-driven manner. The document also defines performance metrics and validation frameworks to measure the platform's effectiveness in enhancing business resilience and improving cyber insurance accessibility. Ultimately, this roadmap serves as the foundation for defining the strategic structure of the ERMIS marketplace.

1.2. Document structure

The document is structured to provide a logical flow of information and is structured as follows:

Section 2 which demonstrates the cyber insurance ecosystem by providing an overview of the cyber insurance market, challenges and practices and the key stakeholders.

Section 3 outlines the business scenarios, presenting real-world use cases that detail, step by step, how stakeholders on both the supply and demand sides engage with the ERMIS marketplace. It also explains the functionality of the bundling engine and its role in integrating cybersecurity and insurance solutions.

Section 4 that details the evaluation methodology for assessing the platform's effectiveness, implementation and deployment roadmap, as well as the validation of KPIs to measure success.

Section 5, the conclusion, which summarises the key points and the anticipated impact of the ERMIS marketplace.

2. THE CYBER INSURANCE ECOSYSTEM

The Cybersecurity Insurance Ecosystem is a complex and interconnected framework that supports organisations in managing risks associated with cyber threats. This ecosystem brings together various stakeholders and services to provide comprehensive coverage, prevention, and mitigation strategies.

Figure 1 "The cybersecurity Insurance Framework"

The ecosystem incorporates critical components, including:

- **Risk Assessment and Analytics:** Tools and insights to evaluate vulnerabilities and predict threats.
- **Incident Response and Forensics:** Investigation and mitigation of breaches swiftly.
- **Cybersecurity Training and Awareness:** Programmes aimed at reducing human errors and increasing preparedness.
- **Compliance and Risk Management:** Adherence to regulatory requirements and effective risk mitigation.
- **Technology and Security Solutions:** Advanced tools to safeguard digital infrastructure.

- **Insurance Brokers and Intermediaries:** Specialists connecting organisations with tailored insurance solutions.

2.1. Market Overview

The cyber insurance industry is rapidly growing due to the increasing frequency and severity of cyberattacks. This market analysis provides insights into the current state and future potential of the cyber insurance services market, which has experienced significant growth in recent years and is expected to keep expanding. According to a report by Allied Market Research, the global cyber insurance market was valued at \$4.3 billion in 2019 and is estimated to reach \$24.8 billion by 2027, growing at a CAGR of 25% from 2019 to 2023, at 20–25% from 2024 to 2027 and over 25–30% until 2031 with potentially reaching \$50 billion or more. This growth is largely driven by the rise in cyberattacks, such as data breaches, ransomware attacks, and phishing attempts, which have increased demand for cyber insurance as organisations seek protection from the associated financial losses and reputational damage. Furthermore, as companies grapple with the complexities of cyber defence and recovery, the role of cyber insurance is becoming an integral part of their overall risk management strategy.

Figure 2 "Global Cyber Insurance Market Size (2019-2031)"

Organisations are becoming more aware of the potential risks posed by cyberattacks, and the increasing adoption of digital technologies and cloud computing has expanded the attack surface for these threats. As businesses embrace digital transformation, they recognise the importance of having adequate insurance coverage to mitigate cyber risks.

Additionally, regulations such as the GDPR¹ in Europe and the CCPA² in the United States, as well as DORA³ and the recent directive of NIS2⁴ which require organisations to protect customer data and notify affected parties in the event of a breach, further drive the need for cyber insurance. Cyber insurance helps organisations meet these regulatory requirements, contributing to the market's growth.

Figure 3 "Global Cyber Insurance Research report

2.1.1. CHALLENGES IN DELIVERING CYBER INSURANCE SERVICES

Delivering effective cybersecurity assurance and insurance services, however, creates several challenges. The ERMIS project aims to address these by developing an integrated platform that combines cybersecurity tools with risk-based insurance solutions. One of the primary challenges is the widespread skill shortage in the cybersecurity field. Many organisations, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), lack the in-house expertise to manage cybersecurity risks effectively. Regulatory complexities, such as navigating various legal frameworks and compliance requirements, add to this difficulty. Furthermore, many businesses still lack awareness of the importance of cybersecurity, which hinders broader adoption of assurance and insurance solutions.

2.1.2 USER FEEDBACK ON CYBER INSURANCE

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>

² <https://oag.ca.gov/privacy/ccpa>

³ https://www.eiopa.europa.eu/digital-operational-resilience-act-dora_en

⁴ <https://www.nis-2-directive.com/>

Feedback from SMEs highlights the need for cybersecurity solutions that are simple to use and cost-effective. Small businesses often do not have the technical knowledge or resources to implement complex cybersecurity measures, so they value tools that are easy to deploy and maintain. On the insurance side, the provision of adaptable policy options and lucid articulation of coverage specifications are of significant importance. Businesses necessitate a readily comprehensible understanding of their cyber insurance provisions, encompassing inclusions, exclusions, and the claims adjudication process. Transparent communication fosters trust and increases the likelihood of businesses adopting these insurance products.

2.1.3 ERMIS PLATFORM AND MARKET CHARACTERISTICS

The ERMIS platform is designed to meet the specific needs of SMEs by combining real-time risk assessment with user-friendly services. This innovative marketplace offers a unique combination of proactive cybersecurity tools and reactive cyber insurance options creating a holistic solution for businesses. Businesses can actively monitor and adjust their security based on current risks and, at the same time, purchase tailored insurance to protect against potential losses. This integration of services makes ERMIS a one-stop solution for businesses looking to enhance both their cybersecurity measures and financial protection.

2.1.4 KEY VARIABLES FOR SUCCESS

To ensure that ERMIS remains relevant and effective, the platform continuously monitors several key variables. These include staying updated on the latest cyber threats to adjust risk assessments accordingly and tracking user engagement to ensure the platform meets customer needs. Analysing insurance claims data helps identify common issues or trends, which can inform the development of better products. Additionally, ensuring compliance with legal and regulatory standards is critical to maintaining trust and ensuring that ERMIS's offerings align with current requirements in the cybersecurity and insurance sectors.

2.2. Marketplace challenges

In creating a comprehensive platform like ERMIS, both technology and regulatory challenges play pivotal roles in determining success. As ERMIS integrates cybersecurity tools and insurance solutions, several factors need to be addressed. These include the seamless integration of diverse technologies and ensuring that the platform remains scalable and reliable. Additionally, understanding and mitigating risk factors such as low cybersecurity awareness and compliance with regulations like GDPR are critical for the platform's adoption. Furthermore, ERMIS faces the challenge of delivering complex cybersecurity assurance and insurance offerings, which require accurate risk assessments and the ability to adapt to different legal frameworks across the EU.

2.2.1. TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS

One of the key technology solutions for ERMIS is ensuring the seamless integration of various cybersecurity tools and platforms, including both EU-funded and open-source solutions. This integration is essential for creating a unified platform that offers diverse capabilities to users without overwhelming them. At the same time, maintaining scalability and reliability is crucial. As the platform grows to accommodate more users and handle larger amounts of data, it needs to proactively handle evolving cyber threats to ensure the continued delivery of effective services without compromising performance or security.

2.2.2. RISK FACTORS

A significant risk factor for ERMIS is the low level of cybersecurity awareness among SMEs, which could slow down the adoption of its services. Many small and medium-sized enterprises do not fully grasp the importance of cybersecurity or the potential impact of cyberattacks on their operations. This lack of awareness could result in hesitation to adopt the marketplace's tools and services. Additionally, ensuring compliance with EU regulations, such as the General Data

Protection Regulation (GDPR), is critical to avoid legal complications. Non-compliance could lead to security breaches or penalties, ultimately damaging the trust and reputation of the platform.

2.2.3. CHALLENGES FOR DELIVERING CYBER SECURITY ASSURANCE AND INSURANCE AS-A-SERVICE

Delivering cybersecurity assurance and insurance as-a-service poses several challenges for ERMIS, particularly in adapting insurance policies to different risk profiles. Effective and flexible insurance offerings depend on accurate risk assessments, which must account for a wide range of business sizes and industries. Another major challenge is navigating the varying legal and regulatory landscapes across EU countries. Differences in laws and regulations make it difficult to create a standardised service that works across all borders, complicating the task of delivering consistent cybersecurity assurance and insurance solutions.

2.3. The cyber insurance process

The general process of establishing a cyber-insurance contract involves several steps and procedures, which are as follows:

2.3.1. ASSESSING RISK

The first step is to assess the level of cybersecurity risk faced by the organisation. This involves evaluating the potential vulnerabilities, threats, and potential financial impact of a cyber-attack or data breach.

2.3.2. IDENTIFYING COVERAGE NEEDS

Based on the risk assessment, the organisation should determine the specific coverage needs for cyber-insurance. This can include coverage for data breaches, network security liability, business interruption, legal and regulatory compliance, public relations, and other related risks.

2.3.3. RESEARCHING INSURANCE PROVIDERS

It is essential to research and identify reputable insurance providers that offer cyber-insurance policies. Consider factors such as their expertise in cyber risk management, policy coverage, reputation, financial stability, and claim handling process.

2.3.4. POLICY SELECTION

Once potential insurance providers are identified, analyse and compare the policies they offer. Carefully review the terms, conditions, coverage limits, exclusions, deductibles, and premiums to ensure they adequately meet the organisation's needs.

2.3.5. PROPOSAL SUBMISSION

Provide detailed information about the organisation's cybersecurity practices, risk posture, and other relevant details to the chosen insurance providers. This allows them to assess risk and provide a customised policy proposal.

2.3.6. UNDERWRITING PROCESS

Insurance providers will conduct their own due diligence by analysing the submitted information, including cybersecurity measures, incident response plans, and risk management practices. They may also conduct audits or request additional information to evaluate the insurability of the organisation.

2.3.7. POLICY NEGOTIATION AND CUSTOMISATION

Once the underwriting process is complete, insurers may provide a policy proposal. This proposal can be negotiated to tailor coverage to the organisation's specific needs. It is crucial to carefully review and understand all terms before finalising the contract.

2.3.8. POLICY ISSUANCE

After negotiations and agreement on policy terms, the insurance provider will issue the cyber-insurance policy document. Make sure to obtain the necessary proof of coverage, declarations page, and any other relevant documents.

2.3.9. PREMIUM PAYMENT

The organisation is required to pay the agreed-upon premium for the cyber-insurance policy. The premium amount is determined by various factors such as coverage limits, deductibles, risk exposure, and the organisation's cybersecurity practices.

2.3.10. POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ONGOING MANAGEMENT

Once the policy is in effect, the organisation should implement the coverage effectively. This includes integrating the policy with existing risk management and incident response plans. Regularly review and update the policy as the organisation's cybersecurity landscape evolves.

2.4. ERMIS Stakeholders

2.4.1. ERMIS SYSTEM ADMINISTRATOR OR IT/ADMINISTRATIVE PEOPLE

It refers to the role that is responsible for the setup and reliable operation of the marketplace. This role ensures the uptime, performance, resources, and security of the computers they manage meet the needs of the other users. The system administrator may require access to the system components and to the registers accounting for the behaviour of the marketplace.

2.4.2. CYBERSECURITY SOLUTION PROVIDER

It refers to the service provider offering tools and technologies that help assess and ensure the security posture of the organisations. Their tools include vulnerability scanners, threat detection systems, penetration testing tools, or security assessment platforms

2.4.3. CYBER INSURANCE PROVIDER

It refers to the company offering coverage for various cyber incidents such as data breaches or business interruption due to cyber threats. It also provides risk mitigation guidance to the companies adopting ERMIS tools.

2.4.4. SME SEEKING CYBER INSURANCE POLICY

It refers to the entity that uses the marketplace to explore and purchase cyber-insurance policy that protects against potential financial losses due to cyber incidents.

2.4.5. SME SEEKING TO IMPROVE THEIR CYBERSECURITY POSTURE

It refers to the entity that uses the marketplace to enhance its cybersecurity infrastructure to lower their risk and reduce premiums.

2.4.6. SME SEEKING A CERTIFICATION OR TRAINING PRODUCTS

It refers to the entity that uses the marketplace to purchase training for its staff or obtain a certification or ensure compliance with the regulatory requirements

2.4.7. OPEN-SOURCE COMMUNITY

It refers to the providers of open-source cybersecurity projects and solutions used in the marketplace that meet fundamental security, privacy and dependability.

3. BUSINESS SCENARIOS

3.1 Terminology

Entity is any legal entity which could be interested in utilising the capabilities of the ERMIS Marketplace. Hence, it includes cybersecurity solution providers, cyber insurance providers as well as any legal entity wishing to or having already insured via the ERMIS Marketplace.

Organisation is any Entity whose name the insurance policy is (also referred to as Insured) or will be (also referred to as Potential Insured) issued via the ERMIS Marketplace.

3.2 ERMIS End Users

ERMIS Administrator: This role is responsible for managing all ERMIS-related tasks. Key responsibilities include creating new organisations, onboarding the initial end user, and approving or rejecting requests for ERMIS-related actions.

Organisation Administrator (OA): This role oversees the administration of a specific organisation that wishes to buy services from ERMIS Marketplace (view assessment results, navigate the ERMIS specific offerings, and manage the organisation's products). Responsibilities are based on the attributes of the specific organisation.

ERMIS End User: This user is part of an organisation to be or having been insured via the ERMIS Marketplace and is assigned by the Organisation Administrator. End users can navigate the ERMIS Marketplace and view policies or data related to their organisation's cyber insurance. However, they cannot edit or delete any information.

Cyber Insurance External Providers (CIEP): A role focused solely on utilising the ERMIS Marketplace to register and manage their cyber insurance offerings. Providers have no access to organisation-specific data or actions.

Cybersecurity Solution External Providers (CSEP): A role focused solely on utilising the ERMIS Marketplace to register and manage their cyber security solution offerings.

Guest: An unregistered user who can navigate and potentially register on the ERMIS Marketplace and view the ERMIS offerings. Guests cannot perform other actions. If they wish to acquire a policy or use the ERMIS solution, they must request the creation of an Administrator or End User account.

3.3 General Use Case – Horizontal Scenario

The general scenario presents the initial steps followed by any entity wishing to register to the ERMIS Marketplace and includes the registration and validation process.

3.3.1. SCENARIO NARRATIVE

SPH, a cybersecurity technology provider, wishes to register to the ERMIS Marketplace. Hence, they enter their business data, such as company name, legal address, legal representative, tax Identification number, and other documentation, to the respective form. The legitimacy of the company is validated by checking the legal name and Tax ID number. In case the legal check fails, the company manually provides the company's certifications needed to be uploaded. These certifications consist of the Certificate of Incorporation, VAT registration certificate, Business license, Insurance certification, Tax Identification Number (TIN) confirmation, etc.

Following the successful submission of the business data, the company has registered to the ERMIS marketplace and the user has gained the credentials. SPH, as an ERMIS registered company, can select the role(s) they will have at the ERMIS Marketplace.

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The available ones include:

- a. Cyber-security Assurance Tool/Technology Provider
- b. Cyber-insurance Provider
- c. Cyber-insured

Based on their interest, they proceed with selecting the Cyber-security Assurance Tool/Technology Provider. At some point, SPH decides that they wish to be cyber-insured through the ERMIS Marketplace. For this reason, they update their profile at the ERMIS marketplace including also the Cyber-insured role in their profile.

3.3.2. SCENARIO STEPS

Scenario ID: Gen-S0	Scenario Name: Navigation of an unregistered user across the ERMIS Marketplace.
<p>Description: This scenario presents the navigation capabilities across the ERMIS Marketplace for an unregistered user.</p> <p>Actors: Guest</p> <p>Goals: To demonstrate that unregistered users can access the ERMIS Marketplace and have a view of its offerings so that they can decide whether they wish to register.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o ERMIS Marketplace is up and running <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o A guest user accesses the Marketplace. o The user is able to view the list of cyber insurance products available at the ERMIS Marketplace along with the cyber security solutions they are linked with. o The user is able to view a demo of the ERMIS Marketplace in order to facilitate their further understanding of its capabilities. <p>Alternative Flows: N/A</p> <p>Postconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The user has gained some experience of the ERMIS Marketplace capabilities and may decide to register their entity (Cyber Insurance External Provider, Cybersecurity Solution External Provider, Organisation Administrator). 	

Scenario ID: Gen-S1	Scenario Name: Request for Entity registration
<p>Description: This scenario will allow the request for the registration of the Entity at the ERMIS Marketplace.</p> <p>Actors: Guest, Organisation Administrator, Cyber Insurance External Provider, Cybersecurity Solution External Provider</p> <p>Goals: To demonstrate that an Entity registers at the ERMIS Marketplace.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p>	

- o ERMIS Marketplace is up and running.
- o The user has all the required data available.

Main Flow:

- o A user enters the Marketplace and decides to register their Entity.
- o The user is prompted to include the requested registration information, such as:
 - User-related data for the admin role such as Last Name, First Name and email.
 - Business data for their entity at the ERMIS Marketplace, including:
 - Entity's name
 - Role(s)
 - TIN
 - VAT number
 - Legal address
 - Country
- o The user accepts the T&Cs of ERMIS marketplace
- o An email or notification is being sent to the ERMIS Admin. If the admin approves the registration, the entity's account and a linked admin account are created.
- o The user that has been registered as an admin is being notified that his/her account has been created and that his/her entity has been registered.

Alternative Flows:

- o The ERMIS admin user rejects the application.
- o No admin nor entity account should be created.

Postconditions:

- o The entity is under registration -not validated- at the ERMIS Marketplace and the admin of this entity has been registered.
- o ERMIS T&C accepted by the Entity (Organisation Administrator, Cybersecurity Solution External Provider, Cyber Insurance External Provider)

Scenario ID: Gen-S2	Scenario Name: Entity Validation
<p>Description: This scenario focuses on the verification of the legitimacy of EU-based Entities by checking their legal name and TIN using a proprietary process.</p> <p>Actors: ERMIS Admin, Organisation Administrator, Cyber Insurance External Provider, Cybersecurity Solution Provider</p> <p>Goals: To validate an Entity registered in ERMIS' Marketplace and allow for the creation of all the relevant accounts</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Entity has already been registered to the ERMIS Marketplace. o A user with ERMIS Administrator role exists for this Entity and can log in 	

Main Flow:

- o ERMIS Administrator clicks on the validation button for the specific Entity.
- o Both ERMIS Administrator and the registered Entity (Organisation Administrator, Cyber Insurance External Provider, Cybersecurity Solution External Provider) are notified about the successful validation of the entity under registration.
- o The ERMIS admin proceeds with the creation of the organisation and the admin account.

Alternative Flows: The company has not been validated. Certifications are provided manually - communication with the entity could be conducted to ensure all relevant information is exchanged efficiently.

Postconditions:

- o The Entity has been validated, and an e-mail was sent to the admin account.
- o Upon logging in, the Organisation Administrator is being requested to update his/her password.
- o The Organisation Administrator can now utilise the ERMIS offerings on behalf of the Entity and/or set up accounts for other users within the Entity.

Scenario ID: Gen-S3	Scenario Name: Creation of end-users of the Entity (optional)
Description: The end users of the Entity for the ERMIS Marketplace are being registered.	
Actors: Organisation Administrator, ERMIS End User	
Goals: Define new users for a specific Entity.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Entity has been registered validated. o The Organisation Administrator account for the specific Entity has been created. o The Organisation Administrator can log in to the ERMIS marketplace. 	
Main Flow:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Organisation Administrator for the Entity chooses to create a new user for the Entity. o They provide all the necessary information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name or nickname ● Role in the organisation ● User email 	
Alternative Flows: N/A	
Postconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The system notifies the Organisation Administrator of the Entity that a new account was created. o The new user of the ERMIS Marketplace is notified about their new account. 	

3.4 Use Case 1 - Supply Side Scenario

3.4.1. OVERVIEW

The supply side scenario describes the preliminary steps needed for the provision of the relevant products to be offered via ERMIS Marketplace. In this preliminary stage, entities offering Assurance and Insurance services that wish to be listed on the ERMIS Marketplace must apply for access by providing basic information about their company profile, products, and services.

3.4.2. SCENARIO NARRATIVE

SPH, a cybersecurity solution provider is looking to expand its market reach and list its offerings on the ERMIS Marketplace by following a structured onboarding process. Following a successful registration and validation of the entity, the provider logs into the platform and initiates the submission of a new cybersecurity solution. The system requests input of key details, including the category of the solution, its name, a brief description, a URL or demo link, user manual instructions, and an overview of how the service is delivered. During this process, the provider must decide whether to allow their solution to participate in a bundled service with cyber insurance products. If they agree, they move forward with the documentation submission process required for validation. Alternatively, if they decline, their solution will remain listed in the marketplace but only for advertisement purposes, without the option to be bundled or sold through the ERMIS platform. Once submitted, an ERMIS administrator is notified via email, and the solution enters the validation process.

Similarly, KAR, a cyber insurance provider looking to offer policies through the ERMIS Marketplace follows the same onboarding workflow. Upon registration and validation, the provider logs in and submits a new cyber insurance policy, entering relevant details such as the geographical coverage, industries and company sizes eligible for coverage, and the types of threats the policy protects against. There is also the option for KAR to contact an ERMIS Administrator for support. To complete the process, they must upload all required documentation to verify the legitimacy of their policy offerings. Once submitted, ERMIS Administrators review the policy and validate its compliance with marketplace standards. Successfully validated policies are then listed on the ERMIS platform, ready to be accessed by potential clients.

These structured processes ensure that cybersecurity solutions and cyber insurance offerings available on ERMIS marketplace meet high-quality standards while fostering collaboration between security providers and insurers to offer complete protection solutions.

3.4.3. SCENARIO STEPS

Scenario ID: SS-S5	Scenario Name: A Cybersecurity Solution Provider includes their Entity's offerings
Description: This scenario is about the listing and provision of all necessary information regarding the offerings of a Cybersecurity Solution External Provider.	
Actors: Cybersecurity Solution External Provider	
Goals: To allow external providers of cybersecurity solutions to include their offerings at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
o The Entity (in this case the Cybersecurity Solution External Provider) has been registered and validated.	
Main Flow:	
o The user logs into the platform.	
o They choose to submit a new Cybersecurity solution.	

- o They are prompted with and fill in a series of information regarding this solution, such as
 - Category
 - Solution name,
 - Solution short description (text),
 - Solution full description (formatted text),
 - Solution URL or Demo,
 - Solution user manual instructions,
 - Short Description of the provision of the selected service
 - o The Entity confirms their willingness for their solution to participate in a bundle service
 - o The user is prompted with the list of the documentation necessary for the validation of the submitted offering.
- Alternative Flows:** The Entity rejects the option to participate in a bundled service, accepting that their solution will be listed on the ERMIS Marketplace for advertisement purposes only, without the ability to be bundled or sold through ERMIS Marketplace
- Postconditions:**
- o The cybersecurity solutions that the Entity wished to include at the ERMIS Marketplace have been submitted.
 - o ERMIS Administrator receives an e-mail requesting the inclusion of the offering(s) in the ERMIS Marketplace.

Scenario ID: SS-S6	Scenario Name: A Cyber Insurance External Provider includes their Entity's offerings
Description: This scenario is about the listing and provision of all necessary information regarding the offerings of a Cyber Insurance External Provider.	
Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider	
Goals: To allow external providers of cyber insurance to include their offerings at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
o The Entity (in this case the Cyber Insurance External Provider) has been registered and validated.	
o The appointed Organisation Administrator of the Entity has been registered and is able to log in at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
Main Flow:	
o The user (Cyber Insurance External Provider) logs into the platform.	
o They choose to submit a new Cyber Insurance policy.	
o They are prompted with and fill in a series of information regarding this policy, such as	
● Countries where the specific policies are provided to	
● Industries that the specific policies cover	
● Size(s) of entities that the specific policies cover (turnover & number of employees)	
● Types of threats that the policy covers	

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- o A field asking the user whether he/she would like to be contacted by an ERMIS administrator regarding the involvement of the offering is being shown.
 - o The user (Cyber Insurance External Provider) is prompted with the list of the documentation necessary for the validation of the submitted offering
- Alternative Flows:** N/A
- Postconditions:**
- o The cyber insurance policies that the Entity wished to include at the ERMIS Marketplace have been added.
 - o ERMIS Administrator receives an e-mail requesting the inclusion of the offering(s) in the ERMIS Marketplace.

Scenario ID: SS-S7	Scenario Name: Validation process for Cyber Insurance Offerings
<p>Description: This scenario focuses on the validation process for the submitted cyber insurance offerings of an Entity.</p> <p>Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, ERMIS Administrator</p> <p>Goals: Adding all the available validation processes.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Cyber Insurance External Provider has included insurance offerings in the ERMIS Marketplace. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The user (Cyber Insurance External Provider) uploads all documents needed, regarding the policies submitted to be offered through the ERMIS marketplace o ERMIS Administrator submits the successful validation of the specific offerings. <p>Alternative Flows: The ERMIS Administrator submits the unsuccessful validation of the Cyber Insurance Provider's offerings and requests additional documentation and/or updates to the offerings to ensure alignment with the provided material.</p> <p>Postconditions: The validated Cyber Insurance Provider's offerings are listed at the ERMIS Marketplace.</p>	

Scenario ID: SS-S8	Scenario Name: Inclusion process for the Cybersecurity Solutions
<p>Description: This scenario focuses on the inclusion of the Cybersecurity solution to be provided by a registered user.</p> <p>Actors: Cybersecurity Solution External Provider, ERMIS Administrator</p> <p>Goals: To ensure that the Cybersecurity solutions offered via the ERMIS Marketplace are validated.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Cybersecurity Solution Provider has already submitted their offerings at the ERMIS Marketplace. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The ERMIS Administrator goes through the submitted Cybersecurity solutions and internally assigns their validation. o The Cybersecurity Solution External Provider shares all documents needed, related to its solutions offered in the ERMIS marketplace. o ERMIS Administrator submits the successful validation of the specific offerings. 	

Alternative Flows:

1. If the validation is not successful, more documentation maybe requested.
2. If the solution is not interested in bundling services
 - . Screening process
 - . Submission of alternative screening process or more communication to be established

Postconditions: All validated cybersecurity solutions submitted by the registered Entity are available at the ERMIS Marketplace.

Scenario ID: SS-S9	Scenario Name: ERMIS Contract Formulation and Signing
Description: The contract between ERMIS and the registered Entity is formulated, signed and submitted.	
Actors: (Organisation Administrator), Cyber Insurance External Provider, Cybersecurity Solution External Provider, ERMIS Administrator	
Goals: To allow for the formalisation of the synergy between ERMIS and the registered Entities via the formulation and signature of the respective contract.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
o The Entity has been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
Main Flow:	
o The user (administrator of the registered Entity) is presented with the ERMIS contract which includes the specific terms of use tailored to them.	
o The user downloads the contract and proceeds with its signing. (TOBA)	
o The user uploads the signed contract at the ERMIS marketplace.	
o ERMIS Administrator is notified that the signed contract has been uploaded.	
o ERMIS Administrator proceeds with the checking of the uploaded signed contract.	
Alternative Flows: The user may negotiate any of the terms of their contract via direct communication with ERMIS.	
Postconditions:	
o The user now has an active contract with the ERMIS Marketplace.	
o The user has signed the TOBA	

Scenario ID: SS-S10	Scenario Name: ERMIS Offerings to Cyber Insurance External Providers
Description: ERMIS offers a set of statistics and analytics services to the Cyber Insurance External Providers.	
Actors: Cyber Insurance External Providers	
Goals: To facilitate the Cyber Insurance Providers in estimating cybersecurity threats and their impacts and making informed decisions about their current and future offerings.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
o The Cyber Insurance External Provider has been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
o The Insured Entities have allowed access to their data for the purposes of the Cyber Insurance External Providers.	
Main Flow:	
o The Cyber Insurance External Provider chooses to view statistical data, such as:	

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- Number of products/sales
 - Number of claims with respect to total companies insured, per size, per industry, per type of incident, per amount of incident, per cybersecurity solution category
 - Threat category impact
- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider chooses to have access to analytics, such as:
- Number of incidents in the past 3-5 years including a breakdown for each year
 - Severity of such incidents and how they impacted day-to-day operation
 - Counter measures deployed to prevent future similar incidents (i.e. ERMIS/other provider tools)
- Alternative Flows:** N/A
Postconditions: The Cyber Insurance Provider has been presented with statistical and analytics data.

Scenario ID: SS-S11	Scenario Name: ERMIS Offerings to Cybersecurity Solution External Providers
<p>Description: ERMIS offers a set of statistics services to the Cybersecurity Solution External Providers. Actors: Cybersecurity Solution External Providers Goals: To allow the Cyber Insurance Solution External Providers to make informed decisions about their current and future tool offerings.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The users using the cybersecurity solutions offered via the ERMIS Marketplace should have allowed access to their data. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Cybersecurity Solution External Provider chooses to gain access to statistics about usage per threat, solution category and sector for further specification <p>Alternative Flows: N/A Postconditions: The Cybersecurity Solution External Providers have been presented with valuable information extracted from cybersecurity solutions' users' anonymised data.</p>	

Scenario ID: SS-S12	Scenario Name: Creation of a bundle
<p>Description: This scenario includes the steps for creating a bundle of cybersecurity and cyber-insurance offerings. Actors: Cyber Insurance External Providers, Cybersecurity Solution External Providers, ERMIS administrator Goals: To make available a bundle of cybersecurity and cyber insurance offerings via the ERMIS Marketplace.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The insurance and cybersecurity solutions to be available at the ERMIS Marketplace <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Cyber Insurance External Provider is notified that potential bundles are available at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider is presented with the list of suggested bundles of cybersecurity solutions with the cyber insurance product(s) they are offering through the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider approves one or more suggested bundles. 	

- o The Cybersecurity Solution External Provider is notified about the new bundle(s) that their solution(s) participate in, as submitted by the Cyber Insurance External Provider.
- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider is notified that the bundle(s) has been created.

Alternative Flows: N/A

Postconditions: The cyber insurance and cybersecurity solution(s) bundle has been created.

3.5. Use case 2 – Demand Side Scenario

3.5.1. OVERVIEW

NDP is a software provider for the National Healthcare Authority. The NDP network is connected to the Healthcare Authorities network through a trusted channel, for the purposes of transferring software from NDP to the Healthcare Authority. Within this scenario, NDP aims at improving its cybersecurity capabilities. NDP wants to get insured from a Supply Chain Attack, which could target the network and servers of the Healthcare Authority through its own network. From the available insurance offerings of the ERMIS marketplace, NDP chooses a cyber insurance offering from KAR.

3.5.2. SCENARIO 2.1 - SELECTION, CUSTOMISATION & DELIVERY (SETUP) OF INSURANCE PRODUCT (BUNDLED WITH ASSURANCE PRODUCTS)

3.5.2.1. SCENARIO NARRATIVE

NDP registers to the ERMIS Marketplace. During this process NDP creates a profile in the ERMIS Marketplace, which includes: a) business information in respect of company size, industry characteristics, contact details etc. & b) technical information in order to create a primary risk profile. NDP is requested to submit documentation supporting their business information, which are validated by ERMIS.

NDP navigates through the ERMIS Marketplace and views the available bundles. They choose a bundle of their interest and view its terms, offerings and prerequisites. The latter include the cybersecurity solutions which should be applied to their infrastructure to be cyber insured and protected. During their navigation through the available bundles, NDP filters the presented bundles based on criteria such as cost and coverage, as well as rank and compare them. Finally, NDP submits interest for a bundle.

NDP uses the required cybersecurity solutions linked with the cyber insurance product of the bundle from the ERMIS marketplace. Through the ERMIS Marketplace the user views the results of the cybersecurity solutions on their infrastructure, which include the available digital certificates along with their issue and expiration date, the conformity assessment checks, the security testing data and the operational evidence, among others. NDP approves the use of this data for the adaptation of the selected bundle based on the assessment results.

NDP is presented with the tailor-made bundle based on the cybersecurity assessment results and accepts the customised bundle. KAR is notified about the bundle request. NDP is presented with the bundle contract, accepts, signs and uploads it. Both NDP and KAR can now view the issued contract in the ERMIS Marketplace under their profile.

At any time point, NDP is able to request for a contract cancellation, a contract amendment, the submission of a claim (scenario 2.2) and the filing of a complaint.

3.5.3. SCENARIO STEPS

Scenario ID: DS-S13	Scenario Name: Potential Insured Entity information provision at ERMIS Marketplace.
<p>Description: The user representing an Entity potentially to be insured provides detailed information. Actors: Organisation Administrator, ERMIS admin Goals: To provide the ERMIS offerings based on the entity’s business and cyber security-wise technological profile.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o ERMIS Marketplace is up and running o The user has all the required data available. o The Entity has already been registered to the ERMIS Marketplace. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The user (Organisation Administrator) enters and submits their business and technical data to their Entity profile at the ERMIS marketplace, such as: business information in respect of company size (turnover previous, current and next year, num. of employees, industry characteristics, contact details etc). o ERMIS admin is notified about the new information regarding the Organisation. o The user (Organisation Administrator) is notified to provide documentation supporting the submitted information. o The user (Organisation Administrator) submits the requested documentation. o ERMIS admin is notified about the submission and proceeds with its check. o ERMIS admin submits successful validation of the provided data. o The user (Organisation Administrator) is notified about the successful validation of their provided information. <p>Alternative Flows: The supporting documentation may not be sufficient for ERMIS to validate the submitted data. Direct communication may be set to clarify open issues and/or requests for adjustment of the provided information in order to be aligned with the documentation.</p> <p>Postconditions: The detailed profile of the Entity serving as a potentially insured entity is available via the ERMIS Marketplace. The Entity can now navigate across available bundles based on the provided business data.</p>	

Scenario ID: DS-S14	Scenario Name: Search for bundles
<p>Description: Scenario for the user to explore and filter cyber insurance products based on criteria like cost and coverage, view prerequisites for testbed tools, and select cybersecurity solutions via the ERMIS Marketplace. Actors: Organisation Administrator Goals: To allow the user to have a clear view of the available offerings in the ERMIS Marketplace and find the one(s) that suit their needs best.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The ERMIS Marketplace is up and running and the cyber insurance products are available. o The Entity is registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Organisation’s profile has been created. <p>Main Flow:</p>	

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- o The Organisation Administrator is able to view the available bundles at the ERMIS marketplace based on their profile data.
- o The Organisation Administrator chooses a bundle of their interest and views its terms, offering and prerequisites in terms of the cybersecurity solutions which need to run on their testbed and provide the assurance and digital certification.
- o The Organisation Administrator filters the available presented bundles based on criteria, such as cost, coverage among others.
- o The Organisation Administrator views the list of bundles linked with each cyber-insurance product.
- o The Organisation Administrator ranks the bundles based on criteria such as cost, coverage among others.
- o The Organisation Administrator chooses two or more bundles and requests for their comparison, the result of which he is presented with.
- o The Organisation Administrator views and compares the available bundles via the ERMIS Marketplace.
- o The Organisation Administrator selects a bundle.

Alternative Flows: N/A

Postconditions: The user has navigated through the available cyber insurance products of their interest in the ERMIS Marketplace and has been informed about their offerings, terms and preconditions.

Scenario ID: DS-S15	Scenario Name: Identification of appropriate bundle
Description: Scenario for the user to express interest in a bundle and approve the use of the profile data sharing with the insurer to receive a tailored cyber-insurance offer.	
Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator	
Goals: To initiate the process for obtaining a particular cyber insurance product	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
o The Entity has registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace.	
o The Entity has been assigned with the role of a Cyber Insurance External Provider.	
Main Flow:	
o The user (Organisation Administrator) selects a bundle and submits a request of interest.	
o The user (Organisation Administrator) approves the sharing of their profile information with the Cyber Insurance Provider offering the selected product.	
o The specific Cyber Insurance External Provider is notified about the expression of interest for the particular product.	
o The user (Organisation Administrator) may communicate with the Cyber Insurance External Provider for setting a common ground about the product.	
Alternative Flows: N/A	
Postconditions: The Organisation Administrator and the Cyber Insurance External Provider set the ground for initiating the establishment of an agreement for the particular selected bundle offering.	

Scenario ID: DS-S16	Scenario Name: Cybersecurity Information about a Potential Insured Entity
Description: Scenario for the entity to be cyber insured to use cybersecurity solutions to generate infrastructure insights, including certificates, assessments, and testing data and share this information with the Cyber Insurance Provider for obtaining a tailored cyber insurance offer.	

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Actors: Organisation Administrator

Goals: For the user to have a clear understanding of their Entity's cybersecurity risk levels based on reliable information and to obtain a bundle offer tailored to their needs.

Detailed Steps of the Scenario

Preconditions:

o The Organisation (Entity to be insured) has used the required solutions linked with the cyber-insurance product of interest from the ERMIS marketplace.

Main Flow:

o The user (Organisation Administrator) can view the results of the cybersecurity solutions on their infrastructure, which include the available digital certificates along with their issue and expiration date, the conformity assessment checks, the security testing data and the operational evidence, among others.

o The user (Organisation Administrator) approves the use of this data for the adaptation of the selected bundle based on the assessment results.

Alternative Flows: N/A

Postconditions: The data necessary for the establishment of a tailor-made cyber-insurance policy have been generated and collected.

Scenario ID: DS-S17

Scenario Name: Finalisation of the cyber insurance contract

Description: Scenario for the user to accept a cyber insurance contract offer, submit a request contract issuance and access the finalised cyber insurance contract uploaded by the Cyber Insurance Provider at the ERMIS Marketplace.

Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator

Goals: To finalise the cyber insurance contract and make it available at the ERMIS marketplace

Detailed Steps of the Scenario

Preconditions:

o All Entities are registered and validated via the ERMIS Marketplace.

o The Organisation Administrator has already submitted a request for an offer regarding a specific cyber insurance offering to the respective Cyber Insurance Provider.

o The Organisation Administrator has already approved sharing of all necessary data with the Cyber Insurance Provider of the specific cyber insurance product.

o Penetration testing legal documents are available.

Main Flow:

o The Organisation Administrator is presented with the tailor-made bundle based on the cybersecurity assessment results.

o The Organisation Administrator of the respective Entity accepts the customised bundle.

o The Cyber Insurance External Provider is notified about the bundle request.

o The Organisation Administrator is presented with the bundle contract.

o The Organisation Administrator accepts and signs the bundle contract.

o The Organisation Administrator uploads the signed bundle contract.

o Both the Entities are now able to view the issued contract in the ERMIS Marketplace under their profile.

Alternative Flows: N/A

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Postconditions: The signed contract regarding the bundle is now available at the ERMIS marketplace. Penetration testing legal documents have been signed.

Scenario ID: DS-S18	Scenario Name: Cyber-insurance contract management
Description: Scenario for the user to request contract cancellation at any time point, amendments or file complaints at any time through the ERMIS Marketplace. Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator Goals: To allow the Insured Entity to manage their cyber insurance contract	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario Preconditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">o All Entities are registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace.o The Insured entity has an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS Marketplace. Main Flow: <ul style="list-style-type: none">o The user (Organisation Administrator) views their available contracts and selects the one of their interest.o The user (Organisation Administrator) submits a request for the cancellation of this contract, indicating the reasons for this decision.o Alternatively, the user (Organisation Administrator) submits a request for amendment of the contract. This amendment may include the terms of performance assessment and the inclusion of newly acquired digital certificateso Alternatively, the user (Organisation Administrator) requests the filing of a complaint to the Insurance Company they have an active or had a contract with.o The Cyber Insurance External Provider views all submitted requests (amendment, cancellation, complaints) by the Insured entities which have an active cyber insurance contract with them via the ERMIS Marketplace. Alternative Flows: N/A Postconditions: -	

3.5.4. SCENARIO 2.2 - CYBERSECURITY INCIDENT, INSURANCE CLAIM SUBMISSION & ANALYSIS

3.5.4.1. SCENARIO NARRATIVE

NDP has an active cyber insurance (in a bundle) contract which is available at the ERMIS Marketplace under the NDP profile.

This contract is under continuous validity assessment by the cyber-insurance company (KAR). During the period being insured, NDP is able to view the frequent policy performance assessment reports via the ERMIS Marketplace. Within this context, NDP can view the available Digital Certificates (including their issue and expiration date) and navigate through the conformity assessment checks, the security testing data and the operational evidence, as instructed and executed from the applied certification models.

If the company (KAR) deems it necessary, requests additional information or updates via notification within the platform.

3.5.4.2. SUB-SCENARIO 2.2.1 - NO POLICY VIOLATION

At some point, a cyber security incident occurs at NDP. Through the ERMIS Marketplace, NDP is notified of the potential threat. After confirming the legitimacy of the incident, NDP is able to submit a claim to the cyber-insurance company (KAR).

NDP receives a request to present the case to KAR, describing the incident and providing the necessary additional information and various technical details. NDP approves access of KAR to the ERMIS evidence linked with the incident. Based on the policy performance assessment of NDP insured infrastructure, no policy violation has been detected on behalf of NDP.

KAR requests the policy performance assessment reports through the ERMIS marketplace and confirms that no cyber insurance policy has been violated. Hence, KAR accepts the submitted claim. At this point, KAR may request for any further information required to reach their decision. KAR finally submits their decision, in this case the acceptance of the claim, at the ERMIS Marketplace.

Through the ERMIS Marketplace, NDP is informed about the acceptance of their claim, after KAR has gone through the assessment reports provided through the ERMIS Marketplace. The process of reimbursement (financial compensation and/or replacement of assets) is initiated. At every step of this process, NDP is notified of the progress status.

3.5.4.3.SUB-SCENARIO 2.2.2 - POLICY VIOLATION

NDP receives an alert of a potential policy violation (e.g., firewall update alert) as indicated by the policy performance assessment via its Marketplace profile. NDP does not act upon this alert. Then a cybersecurity incident takes place at NDP. Through the ERMIS Marketplace NDP submits a claim to the cyber-insurance company (KAR).

NDP receives a request to present the case to KAR. NDP approves access of KAR to the ERMIS evidence linked with the incident.

Based on the policy performance assessment of NDP insured infrastructure, the cyber-insurance policy has been violated. KAR goes through the ERMIS policy performance assessment reports and any accompanying evidence on the NDP insured infrastructure through the ERMIS marketplace.

KAR goes through the provided evidence and reports and concludes that there was policy violation. Therefore, KAR rejects the claim and NDP is informed about this decision. NDP goes through the assessment reports and is able to see the policy violation leading to this decision.

KAR advises NDP for the rejection reasons with a written communication. The advice includes detailed reference to the violated policy terms.

3.5.5. SCENARIO STEPS

Scenario ID: DS-S19	Scenario Name: Normal, day-to-day operation of offerings
Description: Scenario for the Insured entity to have access to the results and findings of the cybersecurity solutions running on their insured infrastructure via the ERMIS Marketplace.	
Actors: Organisation Administrator	

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Goals: To offer any Insured entity via the ERMIS Marketplace access to the evidence generated and collected by the cybersecurity solutions on the insured infrastructure.

Detailed Steps of the Scenario

Preconditions:

- o The Entity has been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace.
- o The Entity has an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS marketplace.

Main Flow:

- o Depending on the cybersecurity solution that the insured entity has allowed to run on their infrastructure, the Organisation Administrator views the list of the different assessments performed at their cyber insured infrastructure at the ERMIS Marketplace.
- o The insured selects and views a specific assessment report.

Alternative Flows: N/A

Postconditions: N/A

Scenario ID: DS-S20	Scenario Name: Policy violation for the normal, day-to-day operation of offerings
Description: Scenario for the Insured entity to receive an alert of a potential policy violation	
Actors: Organisation Administrator	
Goals: To allow for the Insured entity to act upon a detected potential policy violation.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Entity has been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Entity has an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS marketplace. 	
Main Flow:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The user (Organisation Administrator) receives an alert about a potential policy violation (e.g., firewall update alert) as indicated by the policy performance assessment at the ERMIS Marketplace. 	
Alternative Flows: N/A	
Postconditions: N/A	

Scenario ID: DS-S21	Scenario Name: Occurrence of a cybersecurity incident
Description: Scenario for the use of the cybersecurity assessment reports in the context of a cybersecurity incident	
Actors: Organisation Administrator	
Goals: To facilitate incident investigation through the provision of a baseline to assess origin, impact, aid in a swift response and guide remediation efforts, as well as to make an informed decision about whether a claim should be submitted to the Cyber Insurance Provider that they have an active contract with.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Entity has been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Entity has an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS marketplace. o A cyber security incident occurs at the Insured entity's infrastructure. 	
Main Flow:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The user (Organisation Administrator) views the list of available assessment reports for their infrastructure. 	

- o The user (Organisation Administrator) chooses an assessment report of their interest and goes through it.
- o The user (Organisation Administrator) goes through the latest conformity assessment report and evidence relevant to the incident to assess the origin and the impact.

Alternative Flows: N/A

Postconditions: The user (Organisation Administrator) has viewed and collected assessment reports and evidence potentially relevant to the cyber security incident.

Scenario ID: DS-S22	Scenario Name: Claim submission to Cyber Insurance Provider
Description: Scenario for the Insured entity to submit a claim to the cyber insurance provider	
Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator	
Goals: The submission of the claim	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o All Entities have been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Organisation Administrator handles an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS marketplace for their Entity. o A cybersecurity incident has occurred at the Insured entity's infrastructure. o Based on their analysis, the Insured entity has decided to submit a claim to the Cyber Insurance Provider. 	
Main Flow:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o After the cybersecurity incident has occurred at their insured infrastructure, the Organisation Administrator submits a claim to the respective Cyber Insurance Provider via the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider receives a notification about the claim submitted by the Insured entity. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider views a list with all submitted claims by their customers. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider selects the submitted claim for which they received the notification and requests further information regarding the claim. o The Organisation Administrator views the request submitted by the Cyber Insurance Provider to present the case to them, describe the incident and provide the necessary additional information and various technical details. 	
Alternative Flows: N/A	
Postconditions: The claim has been submitted.	

Scenario ID: DS-S23	Scenario Name: Investigation of claim
Description: Scenario for the collection of all the necessary available data in order for the Cyber Insurance Provider to assess the policy violation	
Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator	
Goals: To allow the Cyber Insurance Provider to make an informed decision about the validity of a submitted claim relevant to a cybersecurity incident.	
Detailed Steps of the Scenario	
Preconditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o All Entities have been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. 	

- o The Organisation Administrator handles an active cyber insurance contract at the ERMIS marketplace for their Entity.
- o The Organisation Administrator has submitted a claim for a cybersecurity incident on their insured infrastructure.

Main Flow:

- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider chooses the specific claim submitted to them at the ERMIS Marketplace.
- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider submits a request for access to the policy performance reports and any other ERMIS evidence linked with the specific cyber security incident at the insured infrastructure.
- o The Organisation Administrator approves access for the Cyber Insurance Provider to the ERMIS evidence linked with the event relevant to the claim they submitted.
- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider goes through the provided data along with their dedicated experts and no policy violation is found.
- o The Cyber Insurance External Provider submits their decision accepting the submitted claim at the ERMIS Marketplace.

Alternative Flows:

The Cyber Insurance Provider goes through the provided data along with their dedicated experts and a policy violation is found relevant to the cyber security incident. The Cyber Insurance Provider submits their decision rejecting the submitted claim at the ERMIS Marketplace. The Cyber Insurance Provider provides the rejection reasons.

Postconditions: The decision about the submitted claim is available at the ERMIS Marketplace.

Scenario ID: DS-S24	Scenario Name: Insured’s notification about claim investigation result
<p>Description: Scenario to inform the Insured entity about the claim investigation result</p> <p>Actors: Organisation Administrator</p> <p>Goals: To inform the Insured entity about the decision for their submitted claim following a cybersecurity incident at their insured infrastructure.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o All Entities have been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Organisation Administrator has submitted a claim for a cybersecurity incident on their insured infrastructure. o The Cyber Insurance Provider has made available their decision about the submitted claim at the ERMIS Marketplace. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Through the ERMIS Marketplace, the Organisation Administrator receives a notification that the claim decision is available. o The Organisation Administrator goes through the list of their submitted claims and selects the one of their interest. o The Organisation Administrator views the details of their claim, the acceptance decision and its details. <p>Alternative Flows: If the claim has been rejected by the insurance company, the Organisation Administrator is presented with the rejection reasons with written communication, which includes detailed reference to the violated</p>	

policy terms. Further, the Organisation Administrator goes through the available assessment reports at the ERMIS Marketplace and identifies the policy violation leading to this decision.

Postconditions: The Insured entity has been notified about the Cyber Insurance Provider’s decision regarding their submitted claim.

Scenario ID: DS-S25	Scenario Name: Claim reimbursement
<p>Description: Scenario for informing the Insured entity about the progress of the reimbursement process regarding a submitted claim for a cybersecurity incident at their insured infrastructure</p> <p>Actors: Cyber Insurance External Provider, Organisation Administrator</p> <p>Goals: To keep the Insured entity informed about every step of the reimbursement process.</p>	
<p>Detailed Steps of the Scenario</p> <p>Preconditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o All Entities have been registered and validated at the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider must have accepted the submitted claim via the ERMIS Marketplace. <p>Main Flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The Organisation Administrator of the Insured entity views the list of the claims submitted via the ERMIS Marketplace. o The Organisation Administrator navigates through the claims which have been accepted by the respective Cyber Insurance Provider. o The Organisation Administrator selects a specific claim and views its current reimbursement status. o The Cyber Insurance External Provider updates the current status of the reimbursement process for the accepted claims, when such information is available. o The Organisation Administrator receives a notification about the progress of the reimbursement process. <p>Alternative Flows: N/A</p> <p>Postconditions: The Insured entity gets notified about the reimbursement process status.</p>	

3.6. Business scenarios summary

The following table summarises the ERMIS business scenarios

ERMIS Business Scenario ID	ERMIS Scenarios	ERMIS Scenario Step ID	ERMIS Scenario Step Title
1	Entity Registration, Validation and ERMIS Contract	Scenario ID: Gen-S0	Scenario Name: Navigation of an unregistered user across the ERMIS Marketplace.
		Scenario ID: Gen-S1	Scenario Name: Request for Entity registration
		Scenario ID: Gen-S2	Scenario Name: Entity Validation
		Scenario ID: Gen-S3	Scenario Name: Creation of end-users of the Entity (optional)

ERMIS Business Scenario ID	ERMIS Scenarios	ERMIS Scenario Step ID	ERMIS Scenario Step Title
2	A registered CSEP lists their offerings at ERMIS Marketplace	Scenario ID: SS-S5	Scenario Name: A Cybersecurity Solution Provider includes their Entity's offerings
		Scenario ID:SS-S8	Scenario Name: Inclusion process for the Cybersecurity Solutions
		Scenario ID: SS-S9	Scenario Name: ERMIS Contract Formulation and Signing
3	A registered CIEP lists their offerings at ERMIS Marketplace	Scenario ID: SS-S6	Scenario Name: A Cyber Insurance Provider includes their Entity's offerings
		Scenario ID: SS-S7	Scenario Name: Validation process for Cyber Insurance Offerings
		Scenario ID: SS-S9	Scenario Name: ERMIS Contract Formulation and Signing
4	A registered CSEP uses the ERMIS statistics services	Scenario ID: SS-S11	Scenario Name: ERMIS Offerings to Cybersecurity Solution Providers
5	A registered CIEP uses the ERMIS statistics and analytics services	Scenario ID: SS-S10	Scenario Name: ERMIS Offerings to Cyber Insurance Providers
6	A registered CIEP and a registered CSEP create a bundle	Scenario ID: SS-S5	Scenario Name: A Cybersecurity Solution Provider includes their Entity's offerings
		Scenario ID: SS-S8	Scenario Name: Inclusion process for the Cybersecurity Solutions
		Scenario ID: SS-S9	Scenario Name: ERMIS Contract Formulation and Signing
		Scenario ID: SS-S6	Scenario Name: A Cyber Insurance Provider includes their Entity's offerings
		Scenario ID: SS-S7	Scenario Name: Validation process for Cyber Insurance Offerings
		Scenario ID: SS-S9	Scenario Name: ERMIS Contract Formulation and Signing
		Scenario ID: SS-S12	Scenario Name: Creation of a bundle
7	Contract formulation for a Client	Scenario ID: DS-S13	Scenario Name: Potential Insured Entity information provision at ERMIS Marketplace.

ERMIS Business Scenario ID	ERMIS Scenarios	ERMIS Scenario Step ID	ERMIS Scenario Step Title
		Scenario ID: DS-S14	Scenario Name: Search for bundles
		Scenario ID: DS-S15	Scenario Name: Identification of appropriate bundle
		Scenario ID: DS-S16	Scenario Name: Cybersecurity Information about a Potential Insured Entity
		Scenario ID: DS-S17	Scenario Name: Finalisation of the cyber insurance contract
		Scenario ID: DS-S18	Scenario Name: Cyber-insurance contract management
8	Claim Submission and Investigation with No Policy Violation	Scenario ID: DS-S19	Scenario Name: Normal, day-to-day operation of offerings
		Scenario ID: DS-S21	Scenario Name: Occurrence of a cybersecurity incident
		Scenario ID: DS-S22	Scenario Name: Claim submission to Cyber Insurance Provider
		Scenario ID: DS-S23	Scenario Name: Investigation of claim
		Scenario ID: DS-S24	Scenario Name: Insured's notification about claim investigation result
		Scenario ID: DS-S25	Scenario Name: Claim reimbursement
9	Claim Submission and Investigation with Policy Violation	Scenario ID: DS-S20	Scenario Name: Policy violation for the normal, day-to-day operation of offerings
		Scenario ID: DS-S21	Scenario Name: Occurrence of a cybersecurity incident
		Scenario ID: DS-S22	Scenario Name: Claim submission to Cyber Insurance Provider
		Scenario ID: DS-S23	Scenario Name: Investigation of claim
		Scenario ID: DS-S24	Scenario Name: Insured's notification about claim investigation result

Table 1. Summary of Business Scenarios

4. PILOT EVALUATION PROTOCOL

4.1. Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation methodology for the ERMIS framework will serve as a cornerstone for validating both the technical and functional aspects of the solution, as well as its alignment with the needs of end-users and stakeholders across the pilot activities. The approach will be iterative, evidence-based, and rooted in both qualitative and quantitative assessment methods.

The evaluation will be structured around the following core phases:

- Phase 1: KPI Definition and Refinement
 - The key objective of this phase is to establish a common, agreed-upon set of KPIs across pilots, ensuring measurable outcomes aligned with project objectives and stakeholder expectations.
 - During this phase, the following activities will take place:
 - Collaborative workshops with stakeholders to gather inputs and establish evaluation priorities.
 - Review and revision of existing KPIs (as proposed in the GA), considering project scope, technical feasibility, and stakeholder relevance.
 - Definition of pilot-specific KPIs addressing unique scenarios and performance criteria.
- Phase 2: Formative evaluation
 - This phase will ensure timely identification of challenges and areas for improvement during development and integration stages.
 - This phase will include:
 - Continuous monitoring and iterative testing during implementation cycles.
 - Structured feedback collection through regular technical meetings, developer logs, and sprint reviews.
 - Pilot-specific scenario testing using predefined evaluation scenarios
- Phase 3: Deployment and post-deployment evaluation
 - The objective of this phase is to validate the full-scale deployed solution against the final KPIs, confirming that the ERMIS framework meets intended technical and operational requirements.
 - To achieve this, the following
 - Execution of structured test plans, covering functionality, performance, reliability, and user acceptance criteria.
 - Collection of quantitative data and qualitative feedback
 - Comprehensive pilot demonstrations and evaluation workshops involving end-users, technical staff, and stakeholders.
- Phase 4: Reporting and Feedback Loop
 - Lastly, to ensure transparency of evaluation results and integrate feedback into ongoing ERMIS framework enhancement cycles, ERMIS will employ the following activities:

- Regular dissemination of evaluation reports to project consortium members and external stakeholders.
- Facilitation of feedback sessions to discuss findings and actionable insights.
- Integration of evaluation results into subsequent development and deployment cycles.

The evaluation outcomes will feed into continuous improvement cycles, ensuring that the ERMIS framework evolves responsively and effectively toward a validated, scalable solution.

4.2. Roadmap for Implementation, Integration, and Deployment

This task will deliver a structured roadmap detailing the phased implementation, integration, and deployment of the ERMIS framework across the pilot sites. It will bridge the gap between conceptual design and operational realisation by guiding technical teams, pilot leaders, and end-users through a coordinated transition process.

The roadmap will include the following phases:

- Preparation Phase:
 - Finalisation of pilot requirements and technical specifications
 - Mapping of ERMIS components to pilot scenarios and existing infrastructures
 - Definition of integration constraints, technical dependencies, and data workflows
- Implementation Phase:
 - Incremental development and modular integration of ERMIS core components
 - Setup of pilot-specific configurations and customisations
 - Development of user interfaces, data connectors, and analytics modules
- Integration & Testing Phase:
 - System-level integration within ERMIS-related environments.
 - Execution of the detailed test plan, including functional, interoperability, and stress testing
 - Iterative debugging and refinement based on test results and user feedback
- Deployment Phase:
 - Full-scale deployment of the ERMIS prototype
 - Onboarding of end-users and operational staff
- Post-Deployment Support and Continuous Improvement:
 - Collection of evaluation data as per the methodology described in Section 5.1
 - Regular feedback loops with stakeholders for post-deployment fine-tuning
 - Documentation of lessons learned and best practices for future scalability

4.3. Evaluation and validation of the KPIs

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
1.1	1.1	Number of available tools and services to end users.	>=15	SPH	Deployed cybersecurity-related tools in ERMIS	N/A
1.2	1.1	Level of user acceptance Baseline: 0	>=90%	ZELUS	Surveys and interviews during pilot phases (likert scale, etc)	N/A
1.3	1.2	Number of EU-funded tools/services and components incorporated in ERMIS.	>=10	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite, SPHYNX's Cyber Range ZELUS endpoint security and DFT solution	N/A
1.4	1.2	Number of liaison activities with other EU-funded projects in cyber security	>=5	KAR	Events and workshops with other EU-funded projects	N/A
1.5	1.3	Number of tools and services to cyber insurers	>=5	KAR	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
1.6	1.3	Automation level in cyber insurance processes through ERMIS Baseline 0. No such automation available,	>=90%	KAR	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
1.7	1.4	Increase in the awareness cybersecurity incidents Baseline is currently set to 0 as ERMIS' pilots do not utilise a Cyber Range platform, or training programmes for their staff.	>=10%	SPH	SPHYNX's CR Training Programmes	N/A

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
1.8	1.5	Improvement in the joint automation of individual processes to be integrated into the Marketplace Baseline: Current time needed for a company to receive cyber security insurance services (Insurance workshop feedback)	>=15%	ZELUS	Workflow logs and time comparisons pre/post ERMIS integration	N/A
2.1	2.1	Number of threat analysis models validated	>=3	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite	N/A
2.2	2.1	Accuracy of vulnerability assessment algorithms	>=98%	SPH	SPHYNX' SPA Suite	N/A
2.3	2.2	Improve the vulnerability discovery capabilities Baseline: Currently, ERMIS pilots do not have a way to measure their vulnerability discovery capabilities. Through the use of SPA Suite's vulnerability analyser, they will be able to identify vulnerabilities in their system, from different sources, including the NVD, OSS Index, and other.	>=30%	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite	N/A
2.4	2.2	Percentage of resilience on cyberattacks and on non-malicious failures Baseline: Currently, ERMIS pilots do not	>=95%	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite	N/A

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
		have a way to measure their resilience on cyber-attacks and non-malicious failures. Through the deployment and utilisation of SPA Suite, this will become available.				
2.5	2.3	Number open-source solutions examined in the context of the ERMIS project Baseline: 0	>=10	ZELUS	OSS review logs maintained by ZELUS	N/A
2.6	2.3	Number of new vulnerabilities identified in open-source solutions and reported to ENISA European Vulnerability Database (EVDB)	>=5	SPH		EVDB is not maintained or used anymore. Identifying new vulnerabilities is really difficult and seems to be out of the main target of this project, thus, we would propose to remove this KPI.

DIGITAL-ECCC-2022-CYBER-03-UPTAKE-CYBERSOLUTIONS
D6.1: The roadmap for the validation of cybersecurity assurance and insurance as-a-Service
Dissemination level: Public

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
3.1	3.1	Reduce time to achieve compliance Baseline: 6-12 months	>=20%	KAR	Certification readiness	N/A
3.2	3.2	Increasing automation of the conformity assessment process Baseline:0	>=30%	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite	N/A
4.1	4.1	Number of evidence-based models identified and tested.	>=5	SPH	SPHYNX's ML platform	Due to the lack of historic data around the specification and definition of existing insurance policies, we propose to train UEBA models. Thus, the KPI should be the following: Number of UEBA models trained and deployed

DIGITAL-ECCC-2022-CYBER-03-UPTAKE-CYBERSOLUTIONS
D6.1: The roadmap for the validation of cybersecurity assurance and insurance as-a-Service
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KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
						>=3
4.2	4.1	Evaluate the cyber insurance framework in different domains and business scenarios	>=3	KAR	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
4.3	4.2	Number of generic processes for cyber insurance management tested	>=3	KAR	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
4.4	4.2	Number of generic processes for cyber insurance management validated	>=1	INSU	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
4.5	4.3	Number of technology showcasing activities in several influential and highly attended venues	>=10	INSU	Demonstration in social media networks, conferences and workshops.	N/A
4.6	4.3	Number of SMEs consuming insurance services in their business before the completion of the project	>=10	INSU	Event/workshop with insured SMEs to be organised by the end of the project	N/A
4.7	4.3	Number of consortium partners consuming insurance services in their business Baseline: 0	All technical partners	ZELUS	Insurance contracts from partners/	N/A
5.1	5.1	Number of indicators for all types of evaluation activities Baseline: 0	>=10	ZELUS	Evaluation of framework records/(data)	N/A

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
5.2	5.1	Number of evaluation scenarios designed Baseline: 0	>=6	NDP	Documented scenarios on WP6	N/A
5.3	5.2	Improve cyber resilience and preparedness capabilities of SMEs Baseline: 0 This KPI will improve the cyber resilience and preparedness capabilities for ERMIS pilots, through the use of the SPA Suite, and the Cyber Range platform	>=25%	SPH	SPHYNX's SPA Suite and CR platform	N/A
5.4	5.2	Improve the efficiency and accuracy of the cyber insurance policy management mechanisms. Baseline: Existing applying mechanisms for Cyber insurance policy management.	>=10%	KAR	ERMIS platform demonstration	N/A
5.5	5.2	Lower the mean time to provide conformity assessment on the maturity of open-source projects through automation of the certification process. Baseline: Conformity assessment without the automation process	>=15%	ZELUS	Measuring assessment time/ logs from certification process.	N/A

KPI #	Link to SO	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
6.1	6.3	Number of training programs produced	>=5	SPH	Sphynx's CR platform	N/A
6.2	6.3	Number of trainees engaged with the ERMIS training and cyber range environment	>=50	NDP	Sphynx's CR platform	N/A

Table 2. Evaluation and validation of KPIs

4.4. Impact KPIs

Table XX will describe the Impact KPIs, excluding those that are relevant to the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project, which will be described in D2.2.

KPI ID	Description	Target	Lead Partner	Means to validate	Proposed refinement
iKPI-3	Reduction of time-to-market for security, certification, insurance services through ERMIS marketplace.	>=20%	KAR	Certification readiness	N/A
iKPI-2	Percentage of annual increase of market-ready tools and services in the ERMIS portfolio	>=15=%	KAR	Though the ERMIS future business plan	N/A
iKPI-4	Acceptance level by end users for the provided tools. Baseline: Existing acceptance level of 3 SMEs using cyber security tools, and 10 SMEs using cyber insurance.	>=90%	KAR	More than 11 SMEs accept ERMIS tools.	N/A
iKPI-8	Improve cybersecurity posture by Composite Products. Baseline: 0	>=15%	SPH	ERMIS' Pilot reporting	N/A
iKPI-11	Number of open-source solutions in the ERMIS marketplace	>=15%	ZELUS	Final deployed solution	N/A

Table 3. Evaluation and validation of Impact KPIs

5. CONCLUSION

The ERMIS Marketplace offers an innovative solution that bridges cybersecurity assurance with tailored insurance services, addressing the growing need for integrated, user-friendly cyber risk management—particularly for SMEs.

This deliverable has outlined the structure, functionality, and stakeholder engagement pathways that support the ERMIS framework. Through a comprehensive set of business scenarios, we have demonstrated how both supply and demand side actors can interact with the platform, from registration and validation to bundle creation and policy management. The scenarios highlight the practical workflows enabling seamless interactions between cybersecurity providers, insurers, and insured entities.

The ERMIS pilot evaluation framework ensures continuous improvement and accountability, relying on iterative methodologies, robust KPI tracking, and stakeholder feedback. The roadmap for implementation and integration provides a clear path towards large-scale deployment, supporting the implementation of cybersecurity and insurance-as-a-service in diverse organisational settings. By reducing entry barriers, fostering transparency, and enabling automation of key processes, ERMIS is well-positioned to enhance the cybersecurity resilience and preparedness of European businesses.